

Towards Industry 5.0 Positioning with k -NN-based Enhanced LoRaWAN Localization

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Abstract—The usability of Long Range Wide Area Network (LoRaWAN) for localization remained a white space on the navigation map of modern Industry 5.0 wireless technology. Many traditional approaches proved to be not usable for meaningful accuracy. Nonetheless, this paper serves as a culmination of our investigation into the potential of LoRaWAN for localization, synthesizing our key discoveries and advancement. Besides that, the paper brings two key contributions. First, it introduces two new underground LoRaWAN datasets, serving as assets for researchers and practitioners in the field. Secondly, it proposes two innovative k -nearest neighbors (k -NN)-based algorithms aimed at enhancing position estimation accuracy by optimizing nearest neighbor selection. The integration of the preprocessing strategies with the proposed algorithms leads to accuracy improvement of 17.2%, underscoring the potential of LoRaWAN-based localization in sectors where high precision is not paramount.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, LoRaWAN, localization, measurement error, wearables

I. INTRODUCTION

The increase in safety levels in industries, hazardous factories, and simple organizations where people work alongside robots and smart machines is a long-term process that profoundly affects the structure of the work processes in many companies. Nowadays, this process could be supported and significantly accelerated by modern technologies provided within Industry 5.0 [1], [2]. The core part of the modification and digitalization of the industries gained the concept of the Internet of Things (IoT) and one of its main branches – wearable technology [3].

Wearables can significantly benefit the work safety level, especially in harsh environments and hazardous industries involving autonomous robot actors [4], [5]. This fact has contributed to their widespread adoption in the last decade. However, the trend towards increased functionality, reduced energy costs, and size still poses several complex challenges [6], [7]. Among them, we selected localization, reviewing it through the prism of a niche technology, LoRaWAN.

The authors gratefully acknowledge funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreements No. 813278 (A-WEAR), 956090 (APROPOS), and support grant PN-III-P3-3.6-H2020-2020-0124 from the Romanian Ministry of Research.

LoRaWAN is one of the most well-known and proven communication solutions for IoT operation in general and for industrial wearables in particular [8]. It has enabled many IoT use cases, such as smart cities, smart farming, asset tracking, environmental monitoring, smart waste management, etc. However, at the start of the study, the applicability of LoRaWAN for localization purposes could have been better investigated. The main reason was that the technology was not initially designed for it and had limitations in the form of a small bandwidth, which hints at low accuracy from the beginning [9]. On the other hand, LoRaWAN seems to be an attractive candidate for localization performed by IoT devices because of its low-power profile, big coverage, easy scalability, availability on the market, and higher penetration capabilities compared to frequently used Wi-Fi, BLE, or UWB.

Thus, the research direction in which the article originated explores the possibility of finding a use case for LoRaWAN-based localization using pre- or postprocessing. Progress in this area promises society a low-cost, low-power, wide-range solution that would guarantee sufficient positioning accuracy for wearables, especially for work safety scenarios.

The current article follows and enhances work [9], which presented five open fingerprinting datasets collected using LoRaWAN for indoor, outdoor, and conventional underground environments in Politehnica București National University for Science and Technology (UNSTPB), Romania, and Brno University of Technology (BUT), Czech Republic. While providing a statistical analysis of the collected data, the work also assesses the localization accuracy by comparing trilateration, Weighted Centroid Algorithm (WCA), and several Machine Learning (ML) approaches from regression clustering, claiming k -NN (k -Nearest Neighbors) as the best one.

Utilizing collected datasets and considering previous results, this paper continues investigating the possibilities of increasing the accuracy of LoRaWAN-based localization. Its main contribution consists of two k -NN-based algorithms: reassessment from the origin and from the estimated point. Targeted at a more effective selection of the nearest neighbors for position estimation, these enhancements might interest any task leveraging the k -NN algorithm for data with low fluctuations between neighboring readings. Following [10], it

presents another two underground LoRaWAN-based datasets with the non-local distribution of the equipment (**ds2** and **ds3**), contributing to refining algorithms and serving the research community as a base for experimentation. Finally, the article completes our investigation on the applicability of LoRaWAN for localization by bridging the works published in [9] and [11], presenting the gain in combining the preprocessing techniques and proposed algorithms against the baseline, k -NN, and summarizing the results.

As for the main findings, the paper evaluated LoRaWAN-based localization, finding trilateration and WCA ineffective with 30 meters error, which is not suitable for most industrial applications. On the other hand, ML, in particular k -NN, reduced errors significantly. Redundancy reduction strategies, like averaging and maximum preprocessing, improved accuracy. Indoor datasets were most accurate (2.6 meters), followed by outdoor (4 meters) and underground (5 – 12 meters). Increasing spread factors enhanced accuracy, but optimal gateway numbers varied. New k -NN algorithms and strategy combinations boosted accuracy by 17.2%. While not as precise as leading technologies, LoRaWAN shows promise for applications like logistics and agriculture, achieving around 2.6 meters indoors and 4 meters outdoors under suitable conditions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly introduces the reader to the collected datasets and estimates the baseline localization accuracy, underscoring the importance of preprocessing. Section III presents two k -NN-enhancing algorithms, while Section IV demonstrates the results. Finally, the last section provides the key discussion on the proposed algorithms in terms of LoRaWAN localization and independently and gives the conclusion.

II. BASELINE LOCALIZATION ERROR ASSESSMENT

The results of this paper are based on the previously collected open access LoRaWAN datasets published in [9] and available in [12]. For the sake of coherency, we would like to begin this section with a brief introduction of their setup, proceeding with baseline localization error assessment and comparison of preprocessing techniques.

A. Datasets: description

Two measurement campaigns were organized at BUT and UNSTPB. Each campaign followed the same two-stage procedure: *offline* (preparation of the measurement map, placement of the LoRaWAN LG308 GWs [13]) and *online* (direct collection of the data using LoRa Field Test Devices (FTD) [14]). Further details on organizing measurement campaigns are available at [9].

As a result, seven datasets were obtained [12]. The datasets vary based on initial parameters: environment (indoor aboveground (I), indoor underground (U), outdoor (O)), spread factor (SF), measurement area, number of measurement points (MP), spacing and LoRaWAN gateways (GW). The most important parameters are listed in Table I, while more detailed information on the cases could be found in [12].

TABLE I: Investigated scenarios, each row corresponds to the dataset. I – Indoor; O – Outdoor; U – Underground.

Nº	Location	Meas.	Equip.	Spacing, m	GWs	Env.
ds1	BUT	Building	Building	1	7	I
ds2	BUT	Parking (fl. -1)	Building	~ 3	7	U
ds3	BUT	Parking (fl. -2)	Building	~ 3	7	U
ds4	BUT	Parking (fl. -1)	Parking (fl. -2)	2.5	6	U
ds5	BUT	Parking (fl. -2)	Parking (fl. -2)	2.5	6	U
ds6	UNSTPB	Building	Building	1	9	I
ds7	UNSTPB	Alley	Building	1	8	O

B. Baseline assessment

In a first approximation, localization accuracy was estimated using conventional methods: trilateration, WCA and k -NN. The first two algorithms are dependent on the position of the receivers and can be applied directly without any significant rearranging of the data. Before using k -NN, it is necessary to exclude redundancy caused by multiple fingerprints per location. Within the baseline k -NN, we implemented the *random choice* selection strategy, where one of the fingerprints assigned to a specific location is chosen for further calculations. After removing redundancy, the remaining data was divided into training (20%) and testing (80%) sets. More detailed information regarding the application of those localization algorithms in the current work can be found in the original paper [9].

For the localization error estimation, we applied a widely-utilized Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) metric:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum^K ((x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2)}{K}}, \quad (1)$$

where x and y are real coordinates; \hat{x} and \hat{y} are coordinates of the predicted object coordinates (utilizing Trilateration, WCA, k -NN); K is the number of MPs to be estimated.

Figure 1 shows LoRaWAN localization accuracy estimation for all the investigated scenarios. Here, trilateration and WCA provide a very low accuracy within a few tens of meters, which makes these methods relatively useless for localization purposes. At the same time, k -NN gives much better and generally relatively promising results for most of the scenarios, especially for both indoor scenarios (ds1 and ds6), registering an accuracy of up to 10 times less than was provided by methods dependent on the location of the GWs.

Therefore, k -NN with the random choice was selected as a baseline, while trilateration and WCA were eliminated from the further comparison to avoid overburdening the graphs. Thus, the summary of the baseline results presented in Table II shows an average error of 3.4 m for the indoor environment and 5.3 m for the outdoor environment.

Fig. 1: Localization accuracy for baseline (conventional k -NN without preprocessing).

TABLE II: Baseline minimal mean localization errors.

Dataset	ds1	ds2	ds3	ds4	ds5	ds6	ds7
Error, m	3.4	11.6	13.3	5.6	7.2	3.3	5.3

C. Preprocessing: redundancy reduction strategies

Looking to increase localization accuracy, we experimented with the different redundancy reduction procedures necessary for k -NN. Besides *random choice*, we performed *averaging* (calculations are based on the averaged fingerprint per location) and *maximum* (calculations are based on the fingerprint with the highest average RSSI level) strategies. Figure 2 demonstrates the comparison between the *averaging* and *maximum* strategies, while Figure 3 integrates the best option with the baselines for all the cases.

Fig. 2: Comparison of *averaging* and *maximum* preprocessing strategies.

Fig. 3: Comparison of the best preprocessing option against the baseline.

Analyzing the results presented in the preceding figures, we would like to conclude that:

- While there is no significant difference observed between the two strategies for the given datasets, according to Figure 3 the *averaging* strategy slightly outperforms the *maximum* one. Expectedly, the averaging strategy is predominant for underground datasets characterized by weak signals and general instability. Worth noticing that in [9] the calculations were performed for 5 datasets – without underground ds2 and ds3 – therefore, the results recorded minor dominance of the *maximum* strategy.
- Figure 3 shows a noticeable increase in accuracy when using *averaging* or *maximum* strategies compared to the baseline: gain is distributed in the range from 20 cm to 1.5 m.

Although at this stage the localization accuracy estimates for LoRaWAN have already exceeded initial expectations, they can hardly compete with the leading technologies (UWB: order of cm indoors, GPS: 10 cm outdoors). Therefore, we continued to look for ways to further improve accuracy. The paper in [9] presents experiments both with different parameters of the measurement campaign (SF, number of GWs, spacing) and with ML algorithms. As a result of the analysis, we came to the conclusion that k -NN is the most accurate method for our problem, so we conducted further research on it. Thus, in the next chapter, two extensions of k -NN algorithms are presented.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHMS

When analyzing the dataset using k -NN, one can notice that the shortest distances in the distance matrix can relate to the MPs quite distant from the point to be estimated (this effect was described in detail in our conference paper dedicated to LoRaWAN-based outdoor localization [11]). This primarily indicates the low stability of the signal map, leading to the

wrong selection of the closest neighbors. The idea of the improvement that could be embedded in the k -NN algorithm to decrease the influence of this drawback is to re-estimate the neighbors selected for calculating the unknown position based on the relative distances. In this work, we propose and compare the performance of two modifications described in the following subsections.

A. Modification 1: Reassessment from the origin

The first modification strategy proposes to reassess the relevance of the chosen nearest neighbors based on the Euclidean distance between them and the origin points. As an origin point, one of the corners of the perimeter of the measurement area can be chosen. The idea behind this strategy is that the group of nearest neighbors should be more or less in the same zone. Thus, the proposal is to calculate Euclidean distances from the origin to each neighbor, identify an approximate localization zone based on mean distance value, and neglect outliers, i.e., those neighboring points outside this zone.

The obvious disadvantage of this strategy is that the distance from the origin does not define a specific value but draws a circle, each point representing a possible value. We introduced the second origin point to reduce the localization area and, consequently, decrease the probability of choosing a non-relevant neighbor.

Another aspect is related to the minimal k for which this strategy might be useful: obviously, for the small group of neighbors, the proposal will not work, since it relies on the statistical mean. In this work, k_{min} will be determined empirically: we will calculate the mean localization error for $k = [1, 10]$ and compare the results with the baseline k -NN (see subsection II-B).

Summarizing information above, we have formalized Algorithm 1.

For Modification 1 we have experimented with different tolerances Δ . For the selected results this work presents:

- Modification 1.1: $\Delta = 30\%$.
- Modification 1.2: $\Delta = 50\%$.

B. Modification 2: Reassessment from the estimated value

The second modification is similar to the first one, but the calculation of Euclidean distance is performed from each neighbor not to the origin point but to the preliminary estimated value given by k -NN. The localization zone, in this case, will be determined by one border and stretched between 0 and the mean value of the Euclidean distances plus allowance.

Modification 1 discusses the limits of applicability, pointing out that the strategy will not work at low k , as it relies on the assumption that fewer outliers in the group will exist than relevant neighbors. A similar problem will also be observed in this case: there is a high probability that on the elimination stage, the group of outliers will be bigger than the group of “valid” neighbors, i.e., neighbors that appeared in a localization zone. In this case, elimination of the outliers

Algorithm 1 Reassessment from the origin.

- 1: Calculation of k -NN.
- 2: Calculation of the Euclidean distances between each k neighbors and origin points:

$$dist_{o1k} = \sqrt{(x_{o1} - x_k)^2 + (y_{o1} - y_k)^2}, \quad (2)$$

$$dist_{o2k} = \sqrt{(x_{o2} - x_k)^2 + (y_{o2} - y_k)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where (x_o, y_o) are the coordinates of the origin points and (x_k, y_k) - coordinates of the k th nearest neighbor.

- 3: Calculation of the mean values $dist_{o1k}$ and $dist_{o2k}$:

$$dist_{o1k}^{\bar{}} = \frac{\sum^k dist_{o1k}}{k}, \quad (4)$$

$$dist_{o2k}^{\bar{}} = \frac{\sum^k dist_{o2k}}{k}. \quad (5)$$

- 4: Setting borders to limit localization zone: $dist_{o1k}^{\bar{}} \pm \Delta$, where Δ is a tolerance set as a percentage of the calculated mean distances $dist_{o1k}^{\bar{}}$ and $dist_{o2k}^{\bar{}}$.
 - 5: Identification of neighbors which are not in the localization zone. If no outliers were found, the algorithm terminates. The result of the algorithm is the last evaluation of the position.
 - 6: Elimination of outliers.
 - 7: Position update: calculation of the average coordinates of the remaining neighbors.
-

cannot be justified. To balance this flow, we introduce a condition in which irrelevant neighbors will be eliminated just if their number n will be three times less than the total number of neighbors k : $n \leq k/3$. Thus, we formulate the Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Reassessment from the estimated value.

- 1: Calculation of k -NN.
- 2: Calculation of the Euclidean distances between each k neighbor and origin point:

$$dist_{ek} = \sqrt{(\hat{x} - x_k)^2 + (\hat{y} - y_k)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) are the coordinates of the value estimated via k -NN approach.

- 3: Calculation of the mean value $dist_{ek}^{\bar{}}$ similar to equations (4) and (5).
 - 4: Setting border to limit localization zone: $[0, dist_{ek}^{\bar{}} + \Delta_2]$, where Δ_2 is a tolerance. In this work $\Delta_2 = 5\%$ of the calculated mean distance.
 - 5: Identification of neighbors, which are not in the localization zone.
 - 6: Elimination of outliers if their number, n , satisfies the condition: $n \in [0, k/3]$.
 - 7: Position update: calculation of the average coordinates of the remaining neighbors.
-

TABLE III: Relative advantages of the proposed modifications without preprocessing over the baseline.

Strategy	ds1	ds2	ds3	ds4	ds5	ds6	ds7	\bar{x}
1.1	+1.0%	-	-	-	-	+2.0%	+9.0%	+4.0%
1.2	+3.2%	-	-	-	-	+0.8%	+10.5%	+4.8%
2.1	+4.4%	-	-	-	-	+4.1%	+9.5%	+6.0%
2.2	+1.2%	-	-	-	-	+1.6%	+2.9%	+1.9%

For Modification 2, this work investigates two options:

- Modification 2.1 employs unstable k when the number of nearest neighbors (based on which the estimated position is calculated) is not replenished after eliminating outliers.
- Modification 2.2 uses stable k when the number of removed outliers n is replenished by the next neighbors from the distance matrix d .

IV. SELECTED NUMERICAL RESULTS

The results of testing the proposed modifications without preprocessing (*random choice* selection redundancy strategy) against the baseline (see subsection II-B) are listed in Table III. The average gain in accuracy achieves a maximum of 6% for Modification 2.1. The other versions were less successful: 4.8%, 4%, and 1.9% average increase in accuracy for modifications 1.1, 1.2, and 2.2, respectively.

To estimate the general gain from the modifications proposed in this work, it is necessary to compare them with the baseline using preprocessing, i.e., *averaging* redundancy reduction, which has proven to be the more effective overall. Figure 4 demonstrates an example of such a comparison for the outdoor dataset (ds7), while the whole picture is summarized in Table IV.

Fig. 4: Comparison of the proposed modifications using the outdoors dataset (ds7) as baselinewith the baseline.

The results show that Modification 2.1 remains the most successful, with which it was possible to improve localization quality by 17.2% on average across all datasets, while for datasets 1 and 5, this number exceeds 25%. Among the datasets, the accuracy improvement exceeds 13% for all of them, except ds2 and ds3 – two underground datasets with non-local placement of the GWs.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Summing up the research conducted in [9]–[11] and in this paper, we would like to summarise the key findings in terms of accuracy dependency of LoRaWAN-based localization:

Localization approach. Trilateration and WCA for LoRaWAN-based localization are ineffective, resulting in an approximate error of 30 meters. In contrast, ML algorithms have demonstrated the ability to reduce this error significantly. As shown in [9], among these ML techniques, the k -NN algorithm emerged as the most precise, reducing the mean localization error by up to a factor of 10 compared to the trilateration basis. Among k -NN extensions proposed in this article, the most promising was leveraging reassessment from the estimated position with unstable k .

Redundancy reduction strategy. The baseline k -NN, i.e., k -NN with the random selection of a fingerprint, is noticeably outperformed by *averaging* and *maximum* preprocessing strategies. In turn, the maximizing strategy was marginally surpassed by the averaging one. The application of a particular strategy depends on the average signal level of the dataset: for a low level, the *averaging* strategy is more effective, while for other cases, the *maximum* strategy is preferable.

Environment. Of all the options studied, the highest accuracy is observed for the indoor dataset (~ 2.6 m), followed by the outdoor (~ 4 m) and underground datasets (~ 5 – 12 m).

Combining and enhancing previous research, this paper marks a final step in exploring LoRaWAN’s potential for localization, summarizing key findings and achievements. First, the paper contributes two new underground LoRaWAN-based datasets (ds2 and ds3) with the non-local distribution of equipment, complementing previously published LoRaWAN data and providing a basis for further algorithm refinement and research [12]. Next, the work introduces two novel k -NN-based algorithms: reassessment from the origin and from the estimated point. These algorithms focus on improving the selection process of nearest neighbors for more precise position estimation, particularly useful for tasks using the k -NN algorithm in data with minimal fluctuations between adjacent readings. Further, the article demonstrates the effectiveness of combining *maximum* and *averaging* redundancy reduction strategies with the proposed algorithms, showing the best increase in accuracy of 17.2%.

In conclusion, with the highest recorded accuracies of ~ 2.6 m indoors and ~ 4 m outdoors, this work posits that LoRaWAN-based localization is feasible for both environments under specific conditions (predominantly GW and MP coverage density). Although the accuracy-enhancing

TABLE IV: Relative Advantages of proposed modifications with preprocessing over the baseline.

Strategy	ds1	ds2	ds3	ds4	ds5	ds6	ds7	\bar{x}
1.1	+25.2%	+7.3%	+6.0%	+19.0%	+23.5%	+15.1%	+21.6%	+16.8%
1.2	+25.2%	+7.3%	+5.7%	+19.0%	+24.2%	+12.2%	+21.5%	+16.4%
2.1	+25.9%	+7.3%	+10.3%	+19.0%	+25.6%	+13.4%	+19.1%	+17.2%
2.2	+15.9%	+4.2%	+5.3%	+19.0%	+25.6%	+13.4%	+21.6%	+15.0%
\bar{y}	+23.1%	+6.5%	+6.8%	+19.0%	+24.7%	+13.5%	+21.0%	-

techniques developed in this research do not enable LoRaWAN-based localization to match the leading precision technologies, the approach remains viable for scenarios where extreme localization precision is not critical. It shows particular promise in sectors such as logistics, agriculture, and smart factories, where LoRaWAN is already used for communication and can serve as a backup localization solution.

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